

Restriction of fundamental rights in a context of emergency: COVID 19 and the aspect of autonomy – Can autonomy be limited?

M Shitindo¹

mercury.shitindo@gmail.com

Abstract

Coronavirus disease (COVID-19), an infectious disease caused by a virus that started in china late 2019 and has caused a worldwide pandemic. The world has been affected one way or the other from the outbreak of COVID-19. So far 357,736 have died from it with more than 5,704,736 confirmed infections across the world as at May 29, 2020². Kenya has not been spared either, with numbers steadily increasing day by day. Apart from causing a health crisis, it has created a human, economic and social crisis. There are currently no specific vaccines or treatments for COVID-19, however, there are many ongoing clinical trials evaluating potential treatments. Pandemics of this scale raise pressing medical, ethical, bioethical and organizational challenges. These include global governance, priority setting, allocation of scarce resources and restricting individual liberty – autonomy in the interests of public health. Are there instances where the promotion of autonomy of patients as a means of upholding their respect and dignity impossible?

Key words: *autonomy; beneficence; preparedness; bioethics; patient rights; pandemic*

¹ Mercury Shitindo, Global Bioethics Student at Anahuac University, Mexico.

² WHO Coronavirus Disease (COVID-19) Dashboard. Data last updated: 2020/5/29, 7:02pm CEST.
https://covid19.who.int/?gclid=CjwKCAjw5cL2BRASEiwAENqAPhBAKxYVE5PxYQN1-Qvt_3sFs-KUbjLLWyyAu5nwoCdPAY-B9odWnRoCR4IQAvD_BwE

1. Introduction

This paper seeks to analyze how the aspect of autonomy is accessed during health emergencies. The word *autonomy* comes from the Greek *autos-nomos* meaning “self-rule” or “autonomy”. According to Kantian ethics, autonomy is based on the human capacity to direct one’s life according to rational principles (Meglino 2004; Korsgaard 2004). Rationality, in Kant’s view, is the means to autonomy. Autonomous people are considered as being ends in themselves in that they have the capacity to determine their own destiny, and as such must be respected.

Health emergencies pose a challenge to public health care for both people and populations³. With the current pandemic, physicians face a number of competing duties like duty to patients; duty to protect oneself from undue risk of harm; duty to one's family; a duty to colleagues whose workloads and risk of harm will increase in one's absence; and a duty to society. One of the bioethical challenges facing millions of healthcare workers who provide medical care to patients, millions of patients, and the rest of the population is the aspect of autonomy.

Kenya had the first reported positive case of Covid 19 patient on 13th March, 2020. Almost immediately afterwards an executive order from the president was made. The executive order provided directives, policies and laws that touch on public health, fiscal policies, social status (behavioral) and the administration of justice that have been passed, cited and used by the Government⁴. They are intended to help the control and mitigate the spread of the Covid 19 virus, since the state of exception and suspension of individual guarantees are not adequate measures to control epidemics.

2. Background

What happens if the government is taking the necessary action, but the populace is not doing its share by staying home and washing their hands etc. This is where the challenge begins. The Kenyan President, Uhuru Kenyatta, gave a directive that “anyone who does not follow the directives should be taken to a quarantine facility” (Yusuf 2020). Interim Guidelines on

³ General Health Act. Chapter I. Article 5

⁴ <http://kenyalaw.org/kenyalawblog/kenyas-response-to-covid-19/>

Management of Covid-19 in Kenya, Infection Prevention and Control (IPC)⁵ and Case Management describes quarantine and social distancing as the separation and restricted movement of well persons presumed exposed often at home or may be in designated residential facility or hospital. It can be applied at the individual, family or community level. Until the Ministry of Health establishes the existence of sustained community transmission, all confirmed COVID-19 cases identified should be monitored closely at a health facility isolation room. Contacts of cases are to be quarantined either at home or in designated facilities. Once sustained community transmission has been established, home management of mild cases should be encouraged.

These consolidated guidelines provide recommendations for comprehensive prevention and case management strategies in Kenya. However, adhering to these restrictions has proven challenging to most Kenyans who deem it as unwarranted, unnecessary, an infringement on their rights and most importantly interfering with their ability for self-determination. People have not been turning up for the nationwide mass testing campaign launched by the country's Health Ministry being conducted across the country. During the daily televised briefings from the Ministry of Health on Sunday May 3, 2020, Kenya's chief administrative secretary for health, warned that "COVID-19 testing has so far been a failure in the country", yet the free mass testing is to help the country to flatten the infections curve. The willingness of people to be tested is low, and there was an urgent appeal to Kenyans to willingly come forward to be tested, indicating that experience has shown that countries that have managed to flatten their infection curve quickly have heavily relied on targeted testing.

3. Social responsibility

This brings in the roles and responsibilities, preparedness and response of a state, a nation, a government. While all sectors of society are involved in pandemic preparedness and response, the national government is the natural leader for overall coordination and communication efforts. Kenya's president has been on the forefront in the battle against the pandemic through different measures taken to control the spread. He has delegated different state machineries to enforce this.

⁵ Interim Infection Prevention and Control Recommendations for Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19) in Health Care Settings. Ministry of Health - Kenya. https://www.health.go.ke/wp-content/uploads/2020/04/Kenya-IPC_Considerations_For-Health-Care-Settings-1.pdf

Whilst the ministry of Health has been providing daily briefs on the numbers, fatalities and recoveries from COVID-19.

National preparedness and response is a whole-of-society responsibility. This approach to the Covid-19 pandemic emphasizes the significant roles played not only by the health ministry, but also by all other sectors, individuals, families, and communities, in mitigating the effects of a pandemic. Developing capacities for mitigating the effects of Covid 19 infection is pivotal in dealing with and overcoming such a pandemic.

Despite the appeal, the general populace seems to have varied reasons for their unwillingness for not availing themselves for the Covid 19 tests. One of the reasons resonates with the aspect of autonomy – autonomy. Many do not really understand what is Covid 19 and how it is relevant in their lives. The disease cannot be seen. The people who are “claimed” to test positive are not known to everyone, therefore making it difficult to back up facts. Others associate it with having brought turmoil in their life. There is fear of imagined pain in the testing process, while they are afraid of the pain as those who were tested told them it is painful, and they are afraid of getting the virus since they could be exposed to the ones who getting tested. “They should test us in our homes like how they did it with census. I will not join the crowd there, where the chance of getting the virus is so high. I am 59 years old, and I might die from coronavirus if I get it” that was a remark by an individual. This has been experienced also at hospitals which have reported low hospital visitation for health services, citing fear of contracting the virus, or being assumed to be infected. The ministry of health has assured Kenyans that all hospitals have taken measures to ensure that other services are delivered without putting anyone at risk (Wasike 2020).

4. Principle of autonomy

Human rights have increasingly been put forward as an important framework for bioethics. A standard approach to biomedical ethics, developed by Beauchamp and Childress (2001) in Principles of Biomedical Ethics, resolves ethical issues in terms of four ethical principles: Autonomy, Beneficence & non-maleficence and Justice. Each of which need to be weighed and balanced in determining an optimal course of action. All of these principles require a conversation about the needs and desires of the patient or, in the case of justice, members of

community. The principles are intended to guide. In the case of autonomy, the wishes of the patient need to be determined in order to protect his or her autonomy. This is a question healthcare professionals have to answer almost every day. As they work with patients and families who are making healthcare decisions. Covid 19 has brought this aspect to the fore, querying just how much control should patients have over their healthcare decisions. For a bioethicist, the outright answer would be to give as much control as is feasible. However, when do we know that a patient may not be able to fully control their care decisions? In the face of such a pandemic, where can we find moral action guides when there is confusion and or resistance about what ought to be done?

The very nature of being a physician entails a duty of beneficence to patients. Hence, morally, Physicians have greater obligations to help patients than non-physicians. Beauchamp and Childress (2001) spoke of Beneficence as the principle of acting with the best interest of the other in mind and Non-maleficence as the principle that “above all, do no harm,” as stated in the Hippocratic Oath. Therefore, in the healthcare settings we are required to determine the patient’s views of what does and does not count as goods to be pursued or harms to be avoided. The medical fraternity as a whole also has an implicit contract with society to provide medical help in times of crisis.

5. Patient Autonomy and Informed Consent

All around the world, people have different reasons for fearing to get tested. In Kenya, apart from being infected with the virus, there is the fear of being locked up in a Kenyan quarantine centre. Its currently equated to a prison cell by many, since also those who have been found contravening the laws have been taken to quarantine, if you are a suspected Covid 19 carrier, you and your family are taken to these government-assigned facilities that for some, it’s considered as a less than honorable place to live. Once one is taken to the quarantine facility, they are expected to spend at least 14 days. However, the quarantine period can be extended twice for everyone at centers where someone has shown symptoms of the virus - and they have had to keep paying the bills, with many lamenting of it being impossible to social distance in some of the facilities because of overcrowding. Others spoke of their psychological and mental anguish

after the government extended their stay beyond 14 days. In the words of another quarantine complainant: “It's like you are condemned... it's like you are at the mercy of the government” (Mutahi 2020).

From the above, it can be deduced that there is a semblance of a lack of autonomy or autonomy. There are some individuals who may feel they are not being given the opportunity to choose what happens to them and how. The ethical principle of autonomy, which has many definitions, is highly valued in personal healthcare decision-making. While it is quite correct to say that in some circumstances, other considerations take precedence over the wishes of a person like in instances where their decisions may cause avoidable harm to others – autonomy should be thought of more broadly. Autonomy could be limited when its exercise causes harm to someone else or may harm the patient and or person or if its exercise violates the physician's/healthcare team's medical conscience. Patient wellbeing and autonomy go hand-in-hand. Autonomy should not necessarily be seen as ‘patient control of decision-making,’ but as a clinical reality which consists of education, conversation and concern for patient wellbeing⁶.

It is helpful for healthcare professionals to think of autonomy, not as an immaterial principle or as something that is entirely lost if a right to choose is denied, but rather as a matter of the degree to which it is honored, aimed at providing respectful patient care. The implication is that once information relevant to treatment is made available and the patient is deemed capable of making treatment decisions, then the healthcare professionals proposing treatment should not prevent the patient's decision unless respecting the wishes would cause harm to others, or seriously undermine the patient's wellbeing⁷. Consideration for patient autonomy must always be the starting point for interventions that seek to enhance patients' dignity. Beyond this, the issues must be resolved using appropriate moral reasoning, clear communication, comprehensive assessment of the situation, respect empathy and personal judgement⁸.

⁶ Hospital News, Are there limits to a patient's autonomy in making health care decisions? <https://hospitalnews.com/are-there-limits-to-a-patients-autonomy-in-making-health-care-decisions/>

⁷ ibid

⁸ ibid

John Stuart Mill, expressed that the concept of respect for autonomy involves the capacity to think, decide and act on the basis of such thought and decision freely and independently. further advocating the principle of autonomy (or the principle of liberty as he called it) provided that it did not cause harm to others (Mill 1968). The principle of not causing harm to others (known as Mill's "harm principle") provides the grounds for the moral right of a patient to refuse medical treatment and for a Physician to refrain from intervening against the patient's wishes. Nevertheless, Mill believed that it was acceptable to prevent people from harming themselves provided that their action was not fully informed.

Nowadays, an autonomous decision might be described as one that is made freely/without undue influence, by a competent person, in full knowledge and understanding of the relevant information necessary to make such a decision (Ungerleider et al, 2018). It should also be applicable to the current situation or circumstances. Autonomy or Autonomy in health care, is gradually moving away from a paternalistic approach towards a more individualistic, client-centred approach where the patient plays a more active role in his/her own health and well-being. Such an approach requires that patients take responsibility for making their own decisions and bear the consequences of those decisions.

How does autonomy role play into the current situation whereby the government forces people to go for quarantine, is it for public good or there is infringement of one's fundamental rights and the principle of autonomy and beneficence. Autonomy and individual responsibility shows that the autonomy of persons to make decisions, while taking responsibility for those decisions and respecting the autonomy of others, is to be respected. For persons who are not capable of exercising autonomy, special measures are to be taken to protect their rights and interests. While, Article 6 in the Universal Declaration on Bioethics and Human Rights⁹ on Consent states that any preventive, diagnostic and therapeutic medical intervention is only to be carried out with the prior, free and informed consent of the person concerned, based on adequate information. The consent should, where appropriate, be express and may be withdrawn by the person concerned at any time and for any reason without disadvantage or prejudice. It is important for a patient to be

⁹ Universal Declaration on Bioethics and Human Rights.http://portal.unesco.org/en/ev.php-URL_ID=31058&URL_DO=DO_TOPIC&URL_SECTION=201.html

well informed in order to make an informed decision. Informed consent is a process whereby information is shared with a patient to enable an informed decision. Full disclosure to a patient will empower a patient to make a true informed decision.

Autonomy is a central value in medical ethics. It is plausible that autonomous persons are often in the best position to determine what would be good and bad for them (Sumner 1996) and, consequently, it is arguable that there is good reason to consider patients' autonomy to have instrumental value in their healthcare decisions. Where does public good come in, when should we consider to override this principle. The principle of autonomy acknowledges the positive duty on a health care practitioner to respect the decisions of a patient. The common notion is to protect a person's liberty, privacy and integrity. The relationship between the healthcare practitioner and the patient is based on trust and communication.

The concept of autonomy in the practice of health care has to find a balance between the good of an individual and the good of the community (Engelbrecht, 2014). This tension presents challenges to health care practitioners in Kenya, especially those in the public sector. In essence, autonomy is a manifestation of "one's legal and mental capacity to understand and make an informed decision" (O'Neill 2002). Therefore, to exercise personal autonomy one needs the capacity to understand what is available and whether it is appropriate for one's purpose. Providing information and assistance is the key ethical responsibility of a health care representatives. Providing the legal framework supporting autonomy is the role of legislators. First, to be autonomous (literally a self-lawmaker), an individual must have adequate knowledge to explore and examine all options relevant to the healthcare decision that needs to be made. This specialized knowledge is beyond the scope of most patients, so they must rely on healthcare professionals to present them with the information they lack (often in a simplified version). Furthermore, although a patient may fully understand the medical treatments and consent to it, it can seldom be said the consent and autonomy are truly manifested. A patient will almost never fully grasp all the medical procedures and consequences. In this regard, Caplan (2014) argues that consent is "inherently limited". A patient is not in the position to full predict, let alone comprehend or appreciate all the risks associated with the medical treatments and or procedures.

6. Lack of information

Patients may be quite knowledgeable about their illness, but they usually do not know the whole story. With Covid 19, there is a lot of information and misinformation making it difficult for a person to make an informed analysis that could be considered rational. As we have seen currently, even a physician who becomes a patient may lose objectivity about specific details of treatment. It is the obligation of the healthcare professional who is proposing treatment to provide the relevant information needed to enable the patient to make an informed decision towards the facilitation of their medical treatment, and consequently enhancing their dignity.

The ministry of health in this case, or designated health institution should be tasked with the responsibility of dissemination of information to the public. Using social media and televised advertisement help but only for a few people. This would be mainly people who have access to it and or are already have an idea of what the pandemic entails. An additional effective approach would be to find a mechanism that would relay information directly to the common “*mwananchi*”. This refers to everyone, the common person, children, the vulnerable, the minorities, people living in low income settings and rural areas. Using a person or medium knowledgeable to them would build trust that would give them confidence to make informed decisions on their health. This will also make it possible for everyone to understand the importance of social distancing, safety measures, wearing of masks, lockdown, and others - and that it will require for them to bear with a difficult period economically too albeit only for a period of time. This would definitely eliminate the problem of the unwillingness of people getting tested, or abiding with the safety measures put in place. providing reliable information on the risk, severity, and progression of a pandemic and the effectiveness of interventions used during this pandemic; prioritize and continue the provision of health-care; enact steps to reduce the spread of the virus in the community and in health-care facilities; and protect and support health-care workers during a pandemic. An absence of early and effective preparedness, societies may experience social and economic disruption, threats to the continuity of essential services, reduced production, distribution difficulties, and shortages of essential commodities. Disruption of organizations may also have an impact on other businesses and services. For example, if electrical or water services are disrupted or fail, the health sector will be unable to maintain normal care.

To protect our collective right to health in the current pandemic situation, we need to balance our individual rights with collective responsibilities. In order to fully implement human rights, we need to place more emphasis on the responsibility of all actors, and not just the government and its machinery, to take action together to make sure rights are enjoyed. The health sector (including public health and both public and private health-care services), has a natural leadership and advocacy role in such a pandemic preparedness and response efforts.

While every patient deserves medical care as Article 43(2) of the Kenyan constitution guarantees every person the right to the highest attainable standard of health¹⁰, not all of them should receive the same type of care, for some the treatment will be for healing purposes and for others it will be palliative care. That is why, regarding the issue of the patients to whom resources should be assigned, at all times human dignity should prevail as a fundamental value of medical care and ethical behavior.

Seedhouse (2009), notes that even autonomous people with self-governing capacities sometimes fail to govern themselves in the making of particular decisions because of temporary constraints caused by illness or depression or because of ignorance, coercion, or other conditions that restrict their options. Hence, autonomy may in itself benefit the patient, but it may disadvantage him or her as well. For example, a person who refuses to go for quarantine when they are exhibiting symptoms of Covid 19 may not just be putting their health and those their loved ones at risk, but it may also be difficult for health professionals to carry out their moral duties of doing goods (concept of beneficence), that is to adequately treat any severe symptoms and avoid increased cases of fatalities. Furthermore, Rogers (2002) posits that, when provided with information and the opportunity for greater involvement in making decisions, consumers generally become warier of the treatments offered and make more conservative decisions.

Epstein (2009), asserts that having the freedom to self-govern does not necessarily mean that the agent will simultaneously have the capacity and the opportunity to exercise the right of self-rule. However, the limitation in human, medical and technical resources does not justify abandoning

¹⁰ Article 43 (1) of the Constitution of Kenya, 2010

the ethical and legal obligation of providing care to a patient and ease their suffering, always observing the informed consent and the patient's human rights. Medical intervention should be permitted in a situation where there is evidence of dangerous behaviour. This intervention is permissible in order to prevent any harm to others or self-harm. Society confers professional autonomy and it is limited in comparison to the protection of a patient's autonomy and human rights. The respect for autonomy has only prima facie standing and competing moral considerations can sometimes override it. For example, if our decisions jeopardize public health, potentially harm others, or require a scarce resource for which no funds are available, others can justifiably curb our exercising of autonomy.

Zolkefli (2017), further postulates that, to be genuinely autonomous, we are required to take seriously the social implications of our autonomous decisions. Placing too much emphasis on the promotion of individual patient autonomy, particularly when such decisions are actually made alone, carries the risk that we might forget either the interests of others or the wider public interest (Zolkefli 2017). In this case it would greatly benefit the society if people would cooperate with the medical practitioners and by extension the state. Beginning with the populace willingly accepting to undertake Covid 19 tests.

7. Conclusion

The Bill of Rights provides protection for individual rights including that of autonomy, but all the rights and liberties listed can be limited if the reason is legally justified. One may therefore conclude that autonomy, whilst strongly protected, can be limited in our context under strict rules to enable justice for society and without terminating the rights of the individual patients. The aspect of autonomy remains a good thing in health care, however when faced by calamities, state emergencies or pandemics of the Covid 19 magnitude, we should query if limited autonomy can be justified if it saves a human life or a community. The principles of beneficence, non-maleficence and justice would still come into play. It is important for a patient or would be patient in such extraneous circumstances as now, be given specific and clear information regarding the pandemic. Since most express a sense of fear, it would be the responsibility of the state through medical personnel to help allay their fears and give them the confidence of making right autonomous decisions. Therefore, although there is a compelling argument for promoting

autonomy of patients as a means of upholding respect and dignity for patient autonomy, there is strong evidence that it is not always possible, particularly when the quality of decision and its impact on others are, to an extent, disputed.

References

1. Beauchamp, T. L., & Childress, J. F. (2013). *Principles of Biomedical Ethics*. 7. Aufl New York.
2. Beauchamp, T. L., & Childress, J. F. (2001). *Principles of biomedical ethics*. Oxford University Press, USA.
3. Caplan, A. L. (2014). Why autonomy needs help. *Journal of medical ethics*, 40(5), 301-302.
4. Engelbrecht S. F. (2014). Can autonomy be limited--an ethical and legal perspective in a South African context?. *The Journal of forensic odonto-stomatology*, 32 Suppl 1(Suppl 1), 34–39.
5. Epstein, R. M., & Peters, E. (2009). Beyond information: exploring patients' preferences. *Jama*, 302(2), 195-197.
6. Jonsen, A. R., Siegler, M., & Winslade, W. J. (1982). *Clinical ethics a practical approach to ethical decisions in clinical medicine*.
7. Meglino, B. M., & Korsgaard, A. (2004). Considering rational self-interest as a disposition: organizational implications of other orientation. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 89(6), 946.
8. Mill, J. S. (1968). *Utilitarianism, on liberty, essay on Bentham* (Vol. 140). World Publishing Company.
9. Mutahi, B. (2020). Coronavirus: The fear of being sentenced to a Kenyan quarantine centre. *BBC News, Nairobi*. 20 April 2020
10. Omondi, S., Weru, J., Shaikh, A. J., & Yonga, G. (2017). Factors that influence advance directives completion amongst terminally ill patients at a tertiary hospital in Kenya. *BMC palliative care*, 16(1), 9.
11. O'Neill, O. (2002). *Autonomy and trust in bioethics*. Cambridge University Press.
12. Parker M. (2001). The ethics of evidence-based patient choice. *Health expectations: an international journal of public participation in health care and health policy*, 4(2), 87–91. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1369-6513.2001.00137.x>
13. Rogers, W. A. (2002). Evidence-based medicine in practice: limiting or facilitating patient choice?. *Health Expectations*, 5(2), 95-103.
14. Rowe, K., & Moodley, K. (2013). Patients as consumers of health care in South Africa: the ethical and legal implications. *BMC medical ethics*, 14(1), 15.
15. Seedhouse, D. (2008). *Ethics: the heart of health care*. John Wiley & Sons.

16. Shmerling, H. R. (2020). What's it like to be a healthcare worker in a pandemic? April 08, 2020, 2:30 pm., Harvard Health Publishing. <https://www.health.harvard.edu/blog/whats-it-like-to-be-a-healthcare-worker-in-a-pandemic-2020040819485>
17. Sumner, L. W. (1996). Welfare, happiness, and ethics. Clarendon Press.
18. Ungerleider, R. M., Nelson, K., Cooper, D. S., Meliones, J., & Jacobs, J. (2018). Critical Heart Disease in Infants and Children E-Book. Elsevier Health Sciences.
19. Walzer, M. (1983). Spheres of Justice, Nueva York.
20. Wasike, A. (2020). World, Health, Africa, Latest On Coronavirus Outbreak. "Kenya records low turnout in mass coronavirus testing", East African Country's Health Ministry warns of low willingness of people to be tested for COVID-19" 04.05.2020. <https://www.aa.com.tr/en/africa/kenya-records-low-turnout-in-mass-coronavirus-testing/1828539>
21. Yusuf, M. (2020). Kenyans Confined at Quarantine Facilities See It as Sentence April 22, 2020 03:44 PM <https://www.voanews.com/covid-19-pandemic/kenyans-confined-quarantine-facilities-see-it-sentence>
22. Zolkefli Y. (2017). Evaluating the Concept of Choice in Healthcare. The Malaysian journal of medical sciences: MJMS, 24(6), 92–96. <https://doi.org/10.21315/mjms2017.24.6.11>